

Robust Grasping with Mobile Robots Using Tactile Sensors

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Abstract—Grasping and object manipulation are vital skills for every mobile robot. In real-world applications however, their manipulation performance is often underwhelming. This is in part due to the lack of feedback from the environment during direct physical object contact. In this abstract, we present two novel sensorised end-effector configurations that aim to increase robustness and safety of mobile manipulation. Furthermore, we show how a force controller based on tactile feedback can handle objects more safely than standard position control.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the interest in service robotics has increased both in academia and in industry. Service robots can be thought of as complex mobile systems composed of a variety of sensors and actuators with the goal to accomplish tasks in everyday household settings. As opposed to most stationary robotics setups, one key characteristic of service robots is their mobility. In order for them to be effective in household settings, they need to maneuver these environments safely. The high variability of households combined with noisy sensor readings render this task non-trivial. One of the most demanding tasks for service robots today remains object manipulation, which is reflected by their poor performance in grasping tasks. Object manipulation pipelines often rely on many software components, each being a possible source of providing inaccurate estimates about the environment. Additionally, the nature of a manipulation task necessitates robots to physically interact with their environment, requiring them to be especially careful with their actions. One possible explanation for the poor grasping performance is the lack of feedback from the environment during a manipulation task.

Contrary to service robots, humans excel at object manipulation. When manipulating objects, we rely heavily on sensory feedback provided by tactile afferents in our fingers and hands [1]. They provide us with crucial information about the physical object contact and influence our grasping behavior. Furthermore, they enable us to perform corrective behaviors if a grasp is suboptimal, e.g. in the event of object slippage. Hence, it appears natural for robots to be provided with the same sensory feedback in order to reduce the performance gap.

In this work, we present two novel sensorised end-effector configurations for the TIAGo service robot [2]. One configuration employs a simple form of tactile sensing and is suited to complement control algorithms. The second configuration

Fig. 1. Grasping an object with TIAGo's sensorised parallel-jaw gripper.

produces more complex tactile data and can be utilized to tackle more complex tasks. We also present first results of a force controller that utilizes tactile data to control grip forces rather than positions during grasping.

II. SENSORISED END-EFFECTORS

For the first end-effector configuration, we replaced TIAGo's plastic fingers of its parallel-jaw gripper with strain gauge sensors. Figure 1 shows an object being held using this end-effector configuration. We chose strain gauge sensors as they are affordable, easily customizable and already allow for more robust grasping. They measure the change in resistance of a Wheatstone Bridge that is caused by deformations of the sensor. A LabJack U6 is used to read out this change and convert the analog sensor readings to digital ones. In software, we perform a bias correction of the measurements and transform them into Newtons. Using this setup, we achieve a readout frequency of 180 Hz. This configuration yields one scalar force value per finger, facilitating the development of a force control algorithm using tactile data. The next section explores how such a control algorithm can be developed and how it improves robustness and safety of manipulation.

The second configuration will use a rigid 8x4 tactile sensor array, the Myrmex sensors, to measure object contact. Using these sensor matrices, we receive more data about the object contact at a higher frequency of up to 2 kHz. This allows us to solve more complex tasks such as in-hand object slippage prevention, tactile-based object exploration or texture recognition. [3] uses convolutional neural networks to detect and prevent object slippage using a large 16x16 sensor array, [4] used the same array in simulation to classify

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Fig. 2. Comparison of the final gripper postures of our proposed force controller (left) and position control (right) when grasping an easily deformable object.

object shapes. Currently, this end-effector version is in the integration phase, so we will not report results in this work.

III. FORCE CONTROLLER

We developed a control algorithm that leverages tactile data from the first end-effector version to handle objects more robustly. Similar to [5], our controller is also based on human grasping behavior outlined in [1]. According to Johansson and Flanagan, humans divide their object manipulation tasks into different subgoals, where actions to achieve these goals and transitions are often based on feedback from tactile afferents. They consider the situation where the end-effector (our hand) is already in a pre-grasp pose, meaning that object contact is anticipated when closing the hand. We begin the manipulation with the *reach* phase where the goal is to acquire object contact. Once contact is detected, we transition into the *load* phase. Here, we increase grip force until a certain, pre-determined goal force is reached that is deemed appropriate to handle the object at hand. The authors argue that in order to determine this goal force, we heavily rely on prior knowledge. They reason that, while we are able to perform corrective actions, these can be only small ones as our reaction speed to unexpected events is constrained by the speed of our sensorimotor system. After the goal force is reached, we can execute the manipulation task while maintaining the force and performing small corrections if necessary. Finally, during the *unload* phase, we decrease the grip force gradually until object contact is lost.

In contrast to [5], impose an additional requirement on grasps performed by our controller, namely that of force-closure [6]. For a *force-closure grasp*, the robot can only exert forces on the object that result in a net force of 0 on the object. In a real-world setting, the gripper-object alignment of the pre-grasp pose will rarely be perfect. Therefore, by requiring force-closure, undesired object movements are prevented. When closing the end-effector, our controller checks whether it can satisfy force-closure based on current object contact points. If one finger reaches the object sooner than the other, it stops upon object contact until its counterpart acquires contact as well. As a result, the object is not pushed toward the gripper’s center but is grasped at the position where was located before the manipulation task was initiated.

Figure 2 compares two grasps that were performed on an easily deformable object with different control algorithms. On the left, the object was grasped using our force controller. The object is deformed only very slightly, just to hold it firmly enough in the hand to prevent slippage. The grasp shown in the right image was performed using a standard position control algorithm. It receives no feedback from the environment and closes the gripper by reaching a certain position. By the end of the manipulation task, the object is deformed heavily. When handling delicate objects, classic position control without environmental feedback can be dangerous, as the probability of damaging the object is relatively high.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented two new configurations for TIAGO’s parallel-jaw gripper that employ different kinds of tactile sensors. One configuration was developed to increase manipulation performance by producing tactile data that is well suited for classic control algorithms. The other one incorporates rigid sensor matrices and aims at solving more complex tasks such as slippage prevention or tactile object classification.

We also presented preliminary grasping results of a force controller which is based on tactile data from the first gripper configuration. The controller is inspired from human grasping as well as a theoretical formulation of stable grasps. It is already able to handle objects more safely than standard position control by being able to limit the grasp force directly. In the future, we will incorporate more complex behaviors like slippage mitigation into the controller.

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